

1 **Sapoviruses, a contributor to diarrheal disease worldwide.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We report public health activity associated with Sapovirus infection in man that involves risk for diarrheal diseases.

7 Citations

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